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A Framework for Effective Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment in Post-Mining Areas

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Abstract: This work presents a structured methodology for multi-hazard risk assessment in post-mining coal areas, addressing the complex interactions between natural, mining, and technological hazards. The methodology provides a flexible, semi-quantitative mixed-methods framework designed to evaluate multi-hazard risk scenarios through a seven-step process, which includes identification of hazards, analysis of hazard interactions, and calculation of the Multi-Hazard Index (MHI), Vulnerability Index (VI), and Multi-Risk Value (MRV). The MHI assesses the cumulative intensity of hazard interactions, while the MRV quantifies the socio-economic impacts of various multi-hazard scenarios. The framework also incorporates vulnerability assessments, using social and physical vulnerability indices, to better understand the potential risks to communities. The methodology aims to enhance the safety of post-mining areas by mitigating the cascading effects of hazard interactions and by systematically increasing the knowledge of hazard interdependencies. This approach is adaptable to diverse post-mining contexts, offering a comprehensive framework for assessing and managing multi-hazard risks. It aligns with the broader objectives of the European Green Deal by promoting sustainable land management and addressing the transition of coal regions toward a carbon-neutral economy. It equips stakeholders with necessary tools to enhance resilience and ensure the long-term socio-economic and environmental stability and safety of post-mining areas.

Academic Editor: Raphael Grzebieta

Received: 8 January 2025

Revised: 4 February 2025

Accepted: 13 February 2025

Published: 19 February 2025

Citation: Nalmpant-Sarikaki, D.M.; Theocharis, A.I.; Koukouzas, N.C.; Zevgolis, I.E. A Framework for Effective Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment in Post-Mining Areas. *Safety* **2025**, *11*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/safety11010018>

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Keywords: just transition; vulnerability index; hazard interaction; multi-risk value; sustainable land management; carbon-neutral communities; resilience

1. Introduction

The transition to a carbon-neutral economy, as emphasized by the European Green Deal, is transforming the energy landscape across Europe. A central component of this shift involves the decarbonization of former coal mining regions, which are home to a significant portion of Europe's legacy mining infrastructure. While this transition holds substantial environmental benefits, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions and fostering renewable energy generation [1–3], it also presents considerable challenges. As mining activity ceases, mines close and regions decarbonize, local communities face economic disruptions, job losses, and socio-economic vulnerability [4]. Abandoned coal mines, a byproduct of decarbonization, introduce a complex array of post-mining hazards. These areas continue to affect the environmental stability, socio-economic resilience, and safety of affected communities.

Post-mining areas are characterized by multiple interrelated risks that arise from the degradation of the landscape, environmental contamination, and the long-term legacy of mining activities. These risks are generated from hazards related to ground movement (e.g., subsidence, landslides), environmental pollution (e.g., soil, water pollution), hydrological disturbances (e.g., flood, uplift of groundwater table), and gas emissions or explosions. These hazards pose significant threats to both human health and the surrounding environment.

Currently, risk assessment in post-mining areas remains an underexplored field, primarily because the just transition era has gained attention in recent years. Existing studies on post-mining risk analysis predominantly focus on single-hazard assessment, typically addressing mining-induced hazards without considering the broader multi-hazard conditions that these regions experience. These approaches rely on decision-aid frameworks, such as ELECTRE TRI [5], which are used for risk zoning and prioritization. Additionally, GIS-based simulations [6] and geotechnical modeling methods [7,8] are also used.

Despite the evident multi-hazard conditions present in post-mining areas, very few studies have attempted to address multi-hazard risk analysis in a systematic way. The majority of existing multi-hazard approaches in post-mining areas remain qualitative [9] and semi-quantitative [10], focusing on interaction analyses between different types of hazards, such as mining-induced and natural hazards. The impacts of these hazards are compounded by the ongoing socio-economic disruptions faced by communities reliant on coal mining industries. The need for effective risk management in post-mining areas is paramount, particularly as these regions shift from fossil fuel dependence to a more sustainable, renewable energy future.

As these areas undergo economic transition, former coal industry workers often face job losses and a decline in the region's economic activity, leading to increased socio-economic vulnerability. Existing frameworks for post-mining risk analysis are based on single hazards or specific dimensions of vulnerability, often overlooking the cumulative impacts of multi-hazard interactions and their cascading effects. This creates a significant gap in addressing the diverse and interconnected risks faced by post-mining areas. The framework proposed in this work directly addresses these challenges by providing methods to assess and mitigate hazards in a structured manner. The aim is to increase the safety of these regions while supporting their economic and environmental transition.

This study establishes a multi-hazard risk framework, recognizing that abandoned mining sites often pose interacting hazards. This approach involves assessing the cumulative impacts of multiple hazards, on top of common practices addressing each hazard separately to better manage the complex dynamics of post-mining areas. For instance, land subsidence may disrupt the hydrological system, causing water contamination, while unstable terrain may lead to slope failures. To effectively mitigate these risks and ensure long-term resilience, a holistic, multi-hazard risk management strategy is essential.

The main objective and innovation of this work is to provide a systematic, adaptable framework for understanding and mitigating the complex risks associated with abandoned mining sites. This framework differs from existing ones by quantitatively integrating hazard interactions, assessing multiple dimensions of vulnerability, calculating cumulative risks in post-mining areas. The proposed framework's methodologies integrate the identification and assessment of various hazard interactions and their cumulative impacts. Moreover, it offers a comprehensive risk analysis that informs decision making and enhances their safety. The application in a mining basin scale and the surrounding community takes into account the complex interactions between the post-mining hazards and their related multi-risks. The elements that are affected by hazard interactions are the post-mining areas, the local communities, the population, and

the environment. This work fills the gap in the field by providing mixed-method semi-quantitative approach that handles data limitations while enabling a robust analysis of hazard interactions, cascading effects, and socio-economic vulnerabilities.

Within this work, an effective framework is established for assessing the multi-hazard risks of post-mining areas. It aims to enhance decision-making processes, increase the safety of affected regions, and safeguard the well-being of local communities. The framework seeks to provide a robust foundation for resilience and sustainable land management by addressing the cumulative risks of hazard interactions and integrating socio-economic factors into the analysis. Furthermore, the approach aligns with the European Green Deal's goals of achieving a just transition, ensuring that coal-dependent regions can move toward a carbon-neutral future without compromising their socio-economic stability. This work aims to support decision-making processes by providing a step-by-step framework that integrates both technical and socio-economic factors. This ensures that all relevant dimensions of risk are considered in a comprehensive, transparent, and inclusive manner.

2. Methodology

2.1. Post-Mining Areas

The transition from mining to post-mining areas represents a critical phase in the lifecycle of mining landscapes, involving environmental, socio-economic, and planning challenges. Mining activities leave behind highly altered landscapes characterized by degraded ecosystems, disrupted hydrology, and extensive socio-economic impacts. Successfully transitioning these areas into safe, functional, and sustainable spaces is a complex task that requires integrated approaches [11].

The environmental characteristics of post-mining areas often present significant challenges. In Figure 1, the left side illustrates a typical open-pit mining site, highlighting exposed soils, unstable terrain, and large-scale excavation areas. These landscapes often suffer from issues such as soil erosion, acid mine drainage, and contaminated water systems, which pose threats to both local ecosystems and surrounding communities. The right side of the figure demonstrates the potential for reclamation and redevelopment in post-mining areas. This transition involves stabilizing degraded land and restoring vegetation to create a more balanced and resilient ecosystem. In addition to ecological restoration, integrating renewable energy infrastructure, such as solar farms and wind turbines, can turn these areas into assets for sustainable development. These transformations are not only critical for mitigating environmental risks but also for aligning with broader sustainability goals such as those outlined in the European Green Deal [12]. The figure highlights the potential for economic revitalization through thoughtful post-mining planning. Redevelopment efforts can focus on creating alternative industries, such as agriculture, tourism, and renewable energy production, which provide new employment opportunities and foster economic diversification [13]. Engaging local communities in these processes is essential to ensure that redevelopment efforts align with their needs and aspirations. A participatory approach to planning helps foster social cohesion and long-term sustainability.

Figure 1. A tentative representation of an open-pit mining area transition (left) to a post-mining landscape (right), illustrating environmental rehabilitation, renewable energy integration, and sustainable land use transformation.

2.2. Theoretical Background

The concept of multi-hazard risk assessment is grounded in understanding the interactions among different hazards, especially as they interact with vulnerabilities and affect various risk elements. This approach contrasts significantly with single-hazard risk assessment, which considers each hazard independently, assuming no interactions or compounded impacts between them. In multi-hazard risk analysis, however, it is essential to consider how multiple hazards influence each other and how their combined effects may exacerbate vulnerabilities in a given area. This complexity is particularly relevant in post-mining areas, where the environmental, structural, and socio-economic conditions create a unique and challenging context for risk analysis. These areas are characterized by a combination of natural, mining, and technological hazards. This often results in compounded impacts that require tailored methodologies for effective risk assessment.

Multi-hazard risk assessment involves not just the identification of hazards but also an in-depth understanding of how hazards interact through processes like cascading effects, concurrent occurrences, and cumulative impacts. For example, a primary hazard, such as induced seismicity in a post-mining area, can trigger secondary hazards like land subsidence or flooding, each of which may lead to major effects such as water pollution or landslide. Such events are exacerbated by the degraded environmental conditions typical of post-mining areas. This cascade of effects, known as the ‘Cascading Effect’, provides the foundation for analyzing how initial hazards propagate and magnify additional risks, ultimately compounding the impact on elements at risk. This theory is central to multi-hazard risk analysis in post-mining areas, where environmental degradation, infrastructure vulnerability, and socio-economic challenges are particularly pronounced. It emphasizes the need to prepare for chains of hazardous events, which are essential for comprehensive risk management strategies. However, despite the pressing need, research on multi-hazard risk assessment in post-mining areas remains limited, with most studies relying on qualitative or semi-quantitative methods due to data constraints and the inherent challenges of analyzing complex hazard interactions [9,10,14–16].

Generally, there are three primary approaches to multi-hazard risk analysis: qualitative, semi-quantitative, and quantitative. Each of these methodologies offers distinct benefits and faces specific challenges, making the choice of approach dependent on the research objectives, data availability, and the specific characteristics of the analysis.

Qualitative methods: Qualitative approaches rely on expert knowledge and engineering judgment to identify potential hazard interactions. Tools such as interaction matrices [17–19], diagrams [20], and decision trees [21,22] are commonly used to characterize and visualize these relationships. In multi-hazard studies, these methods can employ color scales or descriptive terms to represent interactions between hazards. Although qualitative

methods provide a simplified view of the hazard landscape, they are valuable for initial assessments, especially when data are limited or when visual representation of interactions is necessary for communication with stakeholders. However, because qualitative methods rely on subjective judgments, they may lack the rigor needed for detailed risk quantification and are often supplemented by more objective analyses.

Semi-Quantitative methods: Semi-quantitative methods bridge the gap between qualitative insights and quantitative precision. These methods combine engineering judgment with computational analyses, using multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) frameworks and GIS tools in several studies [23–27] to assess multi-hazard conditions. Semi-quantitative methods often transform hazard interactions into indicators or assign relative weights to various hazards, reflecting their potential impact on the study area [18,28–30]. This approach is advantageous in scenarios where data availability may be moderate but insufficient for full quantitative analysis. Semi-quantitative methods provide a flexible framework that can adapt to different hazard types, interactions, and scenarios by incorporating both objective data and expert assessment. These methods have shown promise in post-mining contexts, where moderate data availability allows for the integration of both hazard-specific indicators and interaction models. In post-mining areas, these methods are often the starting point, given the scarcity of reliable datasets and the complexity of hazard interactions.

Quantitative methods: Quantitative approaches use statistical and probabilistic tools to rigorously analyze multi-hazard interactions, typically requiring substantial data. Techniques like Bayesian networks [31,32], Copula functions (Ming, Xu [33], Tilloy, Malamud [34]), conditional probabilities [21,35,36], and Monte Carlo simulations [37] are employed to model complex dependencies and to calculate precise risk estimates. Quantitative methods provide the highest level of detail and can produce probabilistic models that account for uncertainties and cascading effects. However, they demand comprehensive datasets and computational resources, which are often unavailable in post-mining contexts due to the challenges of data collection and the inherent complexity of hazard interrelations in these environments. In post-mining areas, data limitations often restrict the applicability of purely quantitative methods, making them most feasible when data coverage is high or when paired with semi-quantitative approaches to maximize both accuracy and adaptability. In post-mining areas, however, the lack of comprehensive datasets often limits the application of these advanced methods, making them more suitable for well-documented case studies or when hybrid approaches are employed.

The selection of multi-hazard risk methodology for post-mining analysis requires careful consideration. Each approach has its strengths. Qualitative methods enable clear visualization and are easily interpretable, making them ideal for preliminary assessments. Semi-quantitative methods, adaptable and moderately data-dependent, are well suited for analyzing a variety of hazard types, including those in post-mining areas where data may be incomplete. Quantitative methods offer robust precision but require extensive datasets, which may not always be feasible. Given these methodological challenges and constraints, indicator-based methods have emerged as a practical and efficient solution for multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment in post-mining areas. Indicator-based approaches provide a structured way to evaluate both vulnerability and multi-hazard intensity across multiple interacting hazards. Indicators—such as environmental, social, and economic factors—are selected to reflect relevant aspects of risk and are combined to create a composite risk profile that can guide decision making and resource allocation.

In an indicator-based methodology, multi-hazard risk is often assessed using a range of indicators that reflect both the intensity of individual hazards and the level of their interaction, as well as the vulnerability of the case study. For example, an indicator-based analysis might include data on past occurrences and intensities of specific hazards,

socio-economic factors, such as population density and economic stability, and physical vulnerability indicators such as infrastructure condition and land use. This approach is effective for both small- and large-scale applications, and can be tailored to specific hazards, such as flooding, landslide, and land subsidence, which are common in post-mining areas. Indicator-based methods also provide a valuable framework for visualizing multi-hazard risks, enabling the development of integrated risk maps that clearly illustrate the cumulative impacts of various hazards. This visualization is crucial for communicating complex risk information to stakeholders and facilitating decision-making processes.

Another advantage of using indicator-based methods in multi-hazard risk assessment is that they support the prioritization of interventions based on vulnerability and exposure levels. By identifying which areas and populations are most vulnerable, decision-makers can allocate resources and mitigation measures more effectively. In post-mining areas, where vulnerabilities often stem from socio-economic challenges and deteriorating infrastructure, such prioritization is essential for developing targeted resilience strategies. Moreover, indicator-based methods are well suited for incorporating both physical and social vulnerability indicators, making it possible to address a wide range of risk factors that contribute to overall vulnerability.

However, indicator-based methods are not without challenges. The accuracy and reliability of multi-hazard risk assessments depend heavily on the quality and availability of data, which can be a constraint in many post-mining areas. To address this, multi-hazard assessments increasingly rely on hybrid methods that combine indicator-based analysis with probabilistic and statistical models, to capture hazard dependencies and enhance risk estimates. These hybrid approaches improve the robustness of risk assessments by incorporating both empirical data and expert judgment, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of multi-hazard interactions and dependencies.

2.3. Methodology Overview

The multi-hazard risk methodology is based on a semi-quantitative, mixed-methods approach. This type of methodology was selected for its adaptability to post-mining areas, where different types of hazards—natural, mining, and technological—can coexist and interact, creating multi-hazard conditions. Given the inherent difficulties in precisely quantifying interactions among different hazard types, a semi-quantitative approach offers the flexibility required to express these interconnections effectively. Additionally, the lack of extensive data in many post-mining areas further supports the choice of a semi-quantitative method, which can work with both available quantitative data and qualitative insights from experts. This mixed-method approach combines two semi-quantitative techniques: one for multi-hazard analysis and another for vulnerability assessment. These techniques use both objective data, such as hazard maps and hazard frequency return periods, and subjective insights generated by experts based on their knowledge and experience.

Various methods are employed for the analysis of multi-hazard interactions. The chosen indicator-based approach, partial multiplication factor method, for multi-hazard analysis was selected for its adaptability and flexibility to fit any post-mining case study. This method's core principle is to enhance the assessment of each hazard's intensity when it interacts with others, effectively capturing the compounded severity and increased impact on the post-mining area in each scenario. Similar criteria guided the selection of the indicator-based approach for vulnerability analysis, which comprehensively addresses both physical and social vulnerabilities of the case study. This approach allows for a holistic risk assessment that reflects the specific dynamics of post-mining areas, providing a nuanced understanding of both multi-hazard scenarios and their potential impacts on vulnerable communities.

The methodology follows four main steps, as illustrated in the flowchart of Figure 2.

Figure 2. Methodological flowchart for multi-hazard risk assessment in post-mining areas.

Multi-hazard analysis: Hazards in each post-mining area are identified, and data are collected from national and European sources to assess each hazard's potential intensity. Interactions between hazards, known as cascading effects, are analyzed and depicted in an interaction matrix. This matrix, along with hazard assessment and specific indicators, is then used to calculate the multi-hazard index (MHI) for each interaction chain, resulting in distinct multi-hazard scenarios for the post-mining area under study. The output of this step is a multi-hazard index for each scenario, which quantitatively reflects the relative overall intensity of its multi-hazard scenario.

Vulnerability assessment: Both physical and social vulnerabilities of the post-mining area are calculated. This stage uses a well-established, indicator-based method widely employed in social vulnerability and resilience calculations. This approach enables a more comprehensive vulnerability index (VI), covering structural, demographic, and socio-economic factors that influence how communities in post-mining areas may respond to hazard impacts, by including both physical and social elements.

Elements at risk: This is the most straightforward component, where end-users provide data on elements at risk. These elements are quantified based on national standards, resulting in an output that expresses the economic value of the assets and infrastructure exposed to hazards within the area. This information is critical, as it enables the integration of economic considerations into the multi-hazard risk assessment.

Multi-risk assessment: The multi-risk value is calculated for each scenario identified in the multi-hazard analysis. For each scenario, the multi-risk value is derived by combining the multi-hazard index, the vulnerability index, and the economic value of elements at risk. This product yields a multi-risk value expressed in monetary terms, allowing decision-makers to assess the impact of each scenario. This approach enables a meaningful and actionable assessment of multi-risk levels, supporting targeted mitigation strategies for post-mining areas, supporting the safety of these areas.

The choice of a semi-quantitative approach in this methodology is primarily driven by the need for flexibility and adaptability in post-mining contexts, where precise quantitative data may be sparse, and multiple interdependent risk factors must be considered. This approach balances objectivity with subjectivity, utilizing both data-driven techniques and expert input to develop a multi-hazard risk framework that can address the unique complexities of each area. The combination of methodologies allows for a balanced assessment, ensuring that each hazard and vulnerability component is weighted appropriately to reflect its impact within a complex, data-limited environment.

The proposed multi-hazard risk assessment framework follows a structured step-by-step approach that integrates various data sources and computational tools to analyze hazard interactions and assess risk in post-mining areas. The framework incorporates multiple methodologies, including spatial analysis, expert-based interaction matrices, and computational risk quantification techniques. Geographic Information System (GIS) is suggested to be utilized for spatial mapping and susceptibility analysis, allowing for the visualization of hazard-prone areas. The assessment of hazard interactions is performed through structured expert judgment using an interaction matrix, which helps quantify cascading effects between hazards. Multi-hazard index calculations and vulnerability

assessment are conducted using a combination of spreadsheet-based weighting methods (e.g., Excel spreadsheets), and programming tools such as Python can be used for more advanced computations. This integration of tools ensures that the framework remains flexible and adaptable to different datasets.

2.4. Step-by-Step Process

This section provides the step-by-step approach for evaluating multi-hazard risks in post-mining areas. The multi-hazard risk method is designed to systematically assess hazard susceptibility, identify hazard interactions, and quantify cumulative impacts across interacting hazards and vulnerable elements. Each step builds upon the previous one, facilitating an organized analysis that captures the complexity of post-mining areas with their hazard interactions. This approach enables decision-makers to derive a comprehensive multi-risk value, helping them prioritize and manage hazards effectively. The following flowchart in Figure 3 illustrates the seven steps of the methodology: beginning with hazard susceptibility (Step 1) and progressing through each phase to the final calculation of the multi-risk value (Step 7).

Figure 3. Flowchart of multi-hazard risk assessment.

Step 1: Hazard susceptibility

In the first step of the multi-hazard risk assessment method, users establish hazard susceptibility by identifying relevant hazards and assessing their potential initial intensity within the study area. This process begins with compiling a comprehensive list of potential hazards based on existing literature, expert knowledge, and stakeholder input. This list should include natural, (post-)mining, and technological hazards that are relevant to the specific conditions of each study area. The goal is to ensure that the identification of hazards is consistent and systematic across different case studies, while also allowing for the inclusion of localized hazards that might be unique to the region.

After selecting the applicable hazards, users assess the susceptibility of each hazard to better understand its potential impact on the post-mining area. This involves gathering local data such as hazard maps, historical records, governmental reports, return period, and other relevant documentation that detail the occurrence and characteristics of each hazard. Based on these data, each hazard is then assigned an initial intensity level from 1 to 3 (1 = low/2 = medium/3 = high), following an increasing scale, where 1 represents minimal intensity and 3 represents very high intensity (Table 1). If quantitative hazard data are lacking, expert judgement can be used to systematically convert qualitative expressions and descriptive information into a scaled format suitable for analysis. Therefore, the output of this step should be as shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Quantitative and qualitative expression of hazard initial intensity.

Quantitative Expression of Hazard Intensity	Qualitative Expression of Hazard Intensity
1	Low
2	Medium
3	High

Table 2. Hazard susceptibility output summarizing identified hazards, their types and intensities.

Hazard	Type	Intensity
Identified hazard 1	Natural/Mining/Technological	1–3
Identified hazard 2	Natural/Mining/Technological	1–3
...
Identified hazard n	Natural/Mining/Technological	1–3

The assigned susceptibility levels provide a foundational understanding of each hazard's significance and potential impact in the region, setting the stage for analyzing hazard interactions in Step 2. This structured approach to hazard susceptibility ensures that hazard susceptibility is evaluated systematically and comprehensively, providing a consistent basis for multi-hazard assessment across diverse post-mining areas.

Example application of hazard susceptibility

Post-mining areas across Europe are often characterized by a range of environmental and geotechnical hazards that arise as a result of past mining activities. These hazards can affect both surface and underground mining sites, with risks varying based on the mining method, geological conditions, and post-closure management strategies. In particular, underground coal mines present unique challenges due to the presence of abandoned mine voids. Across Europe, regions such as the Ruhr coal basin in Germany, the Silesian coalfield in Poland, and the Lorraine basin in France are well-documented examples where underground mining has left environmental risks, including land subsidence, heavy rainfall, and groundwater contamination. To illustrate the hazard susceptibility assessment, consider an indicative post-mining area where land subsidence, heavy rainfall, and groundwater contamination are the primary hazards. These hazards are evaluated based on historical data, geological assessments, and expert judgment to determine their intensity levels.

Land subsidence is a well-documented issue in post-mining areas due to the collapse of underground cavities left behind after mining operations. Severe occurrences have been observed in similar post-mining regions, leading to an intensity classification of high (initial intensity 3). Heavy rainfall contributes to environmental instability, as excessive precipitation can accelerate soil erosion and weaken already unstable terrain. Meteorological records indicate that the area experiences moderate but periodic heavy rainfall, leading to a medium intensity classification (initial intensity 2). Groundwater contamination arises from the leaching of residual mining waste and heavy metals into underground water sources. While documented contamination events have been recorded, they are relatively infrequent, resulting in a low intensity classification (initial intensity 1).

Step 2: Interaction matrix

A fundamental principle of multi-hazard analysis is the understanding of the interaction between hazards, providing critical insights into how hazards influence one another. This step is integral to almost every multi-hazard method, particularly in qualitative and semi-quantitative approaches, as it enables the systematic identification of cascading effects. The interaction matrix is a structured tool used to evaluate and quantify the interactions between the identified hazards from Step 1. This step focuses on understanding how

a primary hazard can influence or trigger a secondary hazard. The interaction matrix provides a visual and quantitative framework to capture these relationships, which is essential for multi-hazard analysis. When interactions between hazards are uncertain, expert elicitation and literature-based assumptions can help define plausible hazard interactions in the absence of detailed historical records.

The interaction matrix is designed in a tabular format where the rows and columns represent the identified hazards. The identified hazards from Step 1, along with their types, are placed on both the vertical (row) and horizontal (column) axes (Figure 4). The vertical axis represents the primary hazards (those that trigger or influence others) and the horizontal axis represents the secondary hazards (those that are affected by or triggered by the primary hazards).

Figure 4. Structure and a tentative application of the interaction matrix showing the interaction levels between hazards, with colored cells indicating the level of interactions: high (red), medium (orange), low (green), and no interaction (white). Diagonal cells are grey, indicating a hazard interacting with itself, and are excluded from this approach.

Each cell ij in the matrix represents the interaction level between the primary hazard i and the secondary hazard j for the specific case study. The interaction levels are categorized into three levels, each represented by a specific color for easy interpretation. Green (low interaction) illustrates minimal influence or triggering potential; orange (medium interaction) illustrates moderate influence or triggering potential; and red (high interaction) illustrates significant influence or triggering potential. Cells where there is no interaction between hazards are assigned white, while diagonal cells (where a hazard would interact with itself) are marked grey and excluded from this analysis (Figure 4). Interaction levels are assigned based on expert judgment, past studies, hazard occurrence records, or other relevant data. The levels should reflect the likelihood of the interaction between each pair of hazards.

A template for constructing the interaction matrix is provided in Figure 4 to standardize the format across the method’s applications. The method for creating the interaction matrix is adapted from [28]. The arrows in the upper matrix of Figure 4 indicate that Hazard 1 (from the vertical axis) triggers Hazard n (from the horizontal axis), represented in cell 1n, with a low interaction level (green cell) in the lower matrix of the same figure. Similarly, Hazard n triggers Hazard 1 with a medium interaction level (orange cell). Cells

with white color represent no interaction between hazards, while the diagonal cells are grey, as these represent a hazard interacting with itself and are excluded from the analysis. The systematic application of this step helps provide a clear understanding of interaction between hazards in each post-mining case study, forming the foundation for constructing multi-hazard scenarios in the next step.

Example application of interaction matrix

After identifying the primary hazards in step 1, their potential interactions must be assessed to understand cascading effects and multi-hazard risks. The interaction matrix in Figure 4 (lower matrix) illustrates these relationships by quantifying how one hazard influences another. For example, heavy rainfall can trigger land subsidence due to soil saturation and increased pore water pressure, leading to a high interaction level between these two hazards. Similarly, land subsidence may exacerbate groundwater contamination by altering subsurface flow paths, potentially increasing the mobilization and spread of contaminants in affected areas. This results in a medium interaction level between land subsidence and groundwater contamination.

Step 3: Multi-hazard scenario

The third step in the multi-hazard risk method involves constructing multi-hazard scenarios, which are sequences of interrelated hazards where a primary hazard triggers secondary hazards, leading to a cascading effect. These scenarios provide a structured representation of how hazards interact and evolve, enabling a realistic assessment of their combined impacts.

The foundation for developing multi-hazard scenarios comes from the interaction matrix constructed in Step 2. Each scenario is based on the interactions identified in the matrix, ensuring that only plausible and data-supported sequences are considered. A scenario must involve at least two hazards, where a primary hazard (e.g., land subsidence) triggers or influences a secondary hazard (e.g., groundwater contamination), and potentially additional hazards (e.g., structural collapse).

The number of potential multi-hazard scenarios is determined by the identified interactions within the matrix. For instance, if numerous hazards and significant interactions exist, the analysis may yield a wide range of possible scenarios. However, the focus should remain on constructing realistic and representative scenarios. This ensures that the assessment is grounded in practical and likely hazard chains rather than theoretical or overly complex combinations. The creation of each scenario follows a sequential approach. Starting from a primary hazard, the analysis traces interactions with subsequent hazards as defined by the interaction matrix. The strength and nature of each interaction guide the inclusion of hazards in the scenario. Hazards with no interactions are excluded.

Figure 5 illustrates the creation of multi-hazard scenarios using a tentative interaction matrix with four hazards. Arrows highlight how interactions between hazards lead to the formation of four distinct scenarios. These visual connections represent the pathways through which one hazard triggers another, clarifying the development process. The output of this step is a table that organizes and illustrates the identified scenarios, providing a clear overview of their structure and relationships. Table 3 presents the multi-hazard scenarios derived from the interactions illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. A tentative interaction matrix showing the creation of multi-hazard scenarios. Arrows indicate the interactions between hazards, while the matrix structure highlights the pathways forming each scenario.

Table 3. Multi-hazard scenarios.

No.	Scenario
1	Hazard 1 → Hazard 2 → Hazard 4
2	Hazard 1 → Hazard 4
3	Hazard 3 → Hazard 2 → Hazard 4
4	Hazard 1 → Hazard 2 → Hazard 3 → Hazard 4

Example application of multi-hazard scenario

Once hazard interactions have been identified in step 2, the next step is to develop multi-hazard scenarios that represent possible sequences of hazard occurrence. These scenarios help visualize how hazards influence each other, providing a basis for risk quantification and mitigation planning. For instance, consider a multi-hazard scenario where land subsidence triggers groundwater contamination. As established in step 2, land subsidence alters subsurface flow paths, potentially increasing the mobilization and spread of contaminants in groundwater. In this scenario:

- Primary hazard: Land subsidence occurs due to the collapse of underground mining cavities, creating depressions on the surface and disturbing the underlying soil and rock layers.
- Secondary hazard: The disruption of geological structures modifies the groundwater system, increasing contaminant migration and leading to widespread groundwater contamination.
- Interaction strength: This cascading effect was previously classified as a medium interaction in the interaction matrix (step 2), meaning that while subsidence does not always lead to groundwater contamination, it significantly increases the likelihood and severity of pollution events.

Step 4: Multi-hazard Index (MHI)

The Multi-Hazard Index (MHI) is a crucial component of this methodology, representing the cumulative intensity of each multi-hazard scenario. It quantifies the overall severity of interacting hazards by considering the adjusted intensities of individual hazards within each scenario. This step enables a comprehensive evaluation of multi-hazard conditions, accounting for the increased intensity resulting from hazard interactions, the adjusted intensity.

Each hazard has an initial intensity (low, medium, or high). However, when hazards interact, their effects can become more severe. To reflect this, their intensity is adjusted using a simple multiplication factor, the so-called adjusted principle. The adjusted principles

(L_k) are numerical values that modify the initial hazard intensity (H_{ini-i}) based on the level of interaction between hazards. These principles account for the compounding effects of interactions; the intensity is slightly increased by low and medium interactions, but it is intensely increased by high interactions (Table 4). When applied, these factors recalibrate the intensity of a hazard to reflect the interaction of its connections with other hazards in the scenario. The methodology provides a realistic representation of hazard dynamics, ensuring that the resulting MHI reflects both direct and cascading hazard effects by systematically incorporating these adjustments. The adjusted intensity for each hazard is calculated using the following equation:

$$H_{adj-i} = H_{ini-i} \times \prod_0^n L_k, \quad n = 0, 1, 2 \tag{1}$$

where:

H_{adj-i} : adjusted intensity of hazard i, the recalibrated intensity of hazard i in the scenario.

H_{ini-i} : initial intensity of hazard i, assigned in Step 1.

L_k : adjusted principle, a value derived from interaction level between hazard i and hazard j (as described in Step 2), with k varying from 1.10 to 1.30 (Table 4).

Table 4. Adjustment principles for hazard-adjusted intensity calculation.

Qualitative Description	Adjusted Principle (L_k)
No interaction	1.00
Low	1.10
Medium	1.20
High	1.30

The multiplication with adjustment principles can involve up to two factors (n up to 2) for a hazard situated between two others: One factor accounts for the interaction with the preceding hazard, and the other accounts for the interaction with the subsequent hazard. Moreover, the interaction levels are categorized into three qualitative levels—low, medium, and high—and are associated with corresponding quantitative adjustment principles. Table 4 illustrates the translation of interaction levels into adjustment principles. White cells in the interaction matrix (indicating no interaction) correspond to an adjustment principle of 1, meaning the hazard’s intensity remains unchanged for that interaction.

For each scenario, the MHI is calculated by summing the adjusted intensities of all hazards:

$$MHI = \sum_1^n (H_{adj-i}) \tag{2}$$

where:

MHI: intensity of each multi-hazard scenario;

H_{adj-i} : adjusted intensity of hazard I;

n: number of hazards within the scenario.

A higher MHI indicates a greater potential impact due to the interaction of hazards.

The output of this step is a table that outlines each multi-hazard scenario alongside its calculated Multi-Hazard Index (MHI). This table provides a concise description of the scenarios and their respective cumulative intensities, serving as the reference for understanding and comparing the severity of multi-hazard conditions across each study area. This step bridges the assessment of individual hazard intensities from Step 1 with the

broader analysis of multi-hazard scenarios, serving as a foundational metric for subsequent steps in the methodology.

Example application of multi-hazard index calculation

Following the identification of multi-hazard scenarios in step 3, the next step involves the calculation of the Multi-Hazard Index (MHI). This index integrates hazard intensity values while incorporating the effects of hazard interactions, providing a computational representation of the overall intensity posed by a given scenario. For the example scenario where land subsidence triggers groundwater contamination, the initial intensity values are derived from step 1. The intensity of each hazard is modified based on interaction effects. Land subsidence (primary hazard) has an initial intensity of 3, but due to its medium level of interaction with groundwater contamination, its adjusted intensity increases to 3.6. Groundwater contamination (secondary hazard) has an initial intensity of 1, but due to its medium interaction with land subsidence, its adjusted intensity increases to 1.2.

Using the MHI formula, the total intensity value for this scenario is calculated as:

$$\text{MHI} = 3.6 + 1.2 = 4.8$$

This value reflects the cumulative hazard potential of the scenario, indicating how the interaction between subsidence and groundwater contamination contributes to overall risk. By quantifying MHI for various scenarios, decision-makers can prioritize high-risk hazard combinations and implement targeted mitigation strategies to minimize cascading effects in post-mining areas.

Step 5: Vulnerability Index (VI)

The Vulnerability Index (VI) represents the combined assessment of social and physical vulnerability in post-mining areas. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the potential impacts of multi-hazard conditions by considering both societal and infrastructural elements. This step adopts and adapts the framework of the Social Vulnerability Index proposed by [38] to address the unique characteristics of post-mining areas. Vulnerability is proposed to be assessed through an indicator-based approach, ensuring that both social and physical aspects are systematically evaluated. The VI is calculated using a set of predefined indicators that capture social and physical vulnerabilities. These indicators are grouped into four categories, as illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5. Group of indicators for vulnerability index assessment.

Indicator Group	Description
Socioeconomic Status	Includes indicators that reflect the economic and demographic profile of the area
Household Composition	Considers the vulnerability associated with the population's age distribution
Environment	Evaluates the urban and agricultural environment
Building and Transportation	Focuses on the characteristics of infrastructure and traffic

The indicators used for this process are:

Below poverty: Represents the proportion of the population living below the poverty line. Areas with high poverty rates are more vulnerable due to limited resources for hazard mitigation and recovery.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per person: Reflects the economic health of the region, with lower GDP indicating reduced resilience to hazards, expressed in monetary terms.

Population under 17 and over 65 years old: Highlights the demographic segments more vulnerable to hazards due to dependency or mobility challenges, expressed in percentage.

Population density (people/km²): Assesses the concentration of people in a given area, with higher densities potentially exacerbating the impacts of hazards.

Settlement area: Measures the extent of inhabited regions, indicating the potential exposure to hazards, expressed in percentage.

Urban and agricultural areas: Differentiates land use, as urban and agricultural areas are impacted differently by hazards, expressed in percentage.

Age of buildings: Older buildings are generally more vulnerable to structural damage during hazard events.

Material of buildings: Evaluates the construction materials, with certain materials offering better resistance to specific hazards.

Geometry of Buildings: Considers the complexity of building designs, as irregular geometries may be more susceptible to damage.

Traffic Area: Reflects the transportation network's vulnerability, which is critical for emergency response and evacuation, expressed in percentage.

After gathering data and assigning final values to the selected indicators, the process of calculating the Vulnerability Index (VI) begins. This structured procedure transforms raw data into a meaningful composite index, reflecting both social and physical vulnerability. This step ensures a balanced and transparent calculation by systematically analyzing indicator values, applying group weights, and aggregating results. The VI calculation follows these steps:

Indicator value assessment: Each indicator's value is determined based on European, national, or local standards. These values range across a nine-point scale, where the lowest part of the range is assigned a value of 1, and the highest part is assigned a value of 9. For example, if an indicator value falls within the fifth sub-range, it is assigned a score of 5. However, in cases where detailed socio-economic or structural vulnerability data are unavailable, proxy indicators (e.g., census data, infrastructure maps) and participatory assessments can serve as alternative sources.

Weight assignment: Each group (socioeconomic status, household composition, environment, and building and transportation) is weighted differently for each case study. These weights reflect the relative importance of each group in the specific case study. The sum of the weights assigned to all groups must equal one to ensure a balanced contribution to the overall VI calculation.

Group score calculation: The average of the indicator scores within each group is calculated and multiplied by the assigned weight for that group.

Aggregation of group scores: The weighted scores of all groups are summed to obtain the overall VI for the study area.

Each post-mining area represents a dynamic system with distinct socio-economic, environmental, and infrastructural characteristics. As a result, determining a fixed set of weights for the vulnerability indicators across different case studies remains a challenge. Further refinement of this weighting approach is necessary to establish a more standardized methodology for post-mining areas. Future research should explore advanced weighting techniques, such as expert judgment, statistical approaches, or subjective multi-criteria decision-making methods, to enhance the robustness of the assessment.

In the existing literature on indicator-based vulnerability assessments, a common approach is to apply equal weights to all indicators due to the lack of precise justification for assigning different weights [39]. While this method ensures simplicity and consistency, this assumption has been recognized as a limitation, as it does not fully capture the varying degrees of importance among vulnerability factors. Further work is needed to refine

and validate this aspect of the framework. Moreover, data availability remains a broader challenge throughout multiple steps of the framework (e.g., step 1, step 2, and step 5), as datasets are required to evaluate the proposed methodology. Addressing data limitations at these critical stages is essential for ensuring reliable and transferable risk assessments.

To evaluate the sensitivity of the results to the weighting scheme, different weighting scenarios (not presented in this work) were tested to observe their impact on the final VI values. Preliminary findings indicate that variations in weight assignment can influence the ranking of areas in terms of vulnerability, particularly when certain indicators have disproportionately high or low weights [40]. However, the overall pattern of vulnerable areas remains relatively stable, suggesting that while the specific values of the VI may shift, the general classification of high- and low-vulnerability areas is not drastically altered. A formal sensitivity analysis, such as varying the weights systematically and assessing the changes in VI rankings, could further validate the robustness of the approach.

The final VI reflects the combined social and physical vulnerabilities in the study area, providing a key input for assessing multi-risk scenarios in subsequent steps. This value enables decision-makers to prioritize mitigation measures and enhance resilience in the most vulnerable areas. Figure 6, illustrating this process, is provided below, showing the flow from individual indicators to the final VI calculation. This figure clarifies the relationship between indicator values, group weights, and the overall vulnerability index calculation. The structured approach of Step 5 ensures that the multi-hazard risk assessment incorporates a robust understanding of vulnerabilities, tailored to the specific characteristics of post-mining areas.

Figure 6. Framework of Vulnerability Index (VI) calculation.

Step 6: Elements at risk (EAR)

The elements at risk (EAR) represent the components within an area that are exposed to multi-hazard conditions and are likely to be affected. These elements are critical to this methodology, as they provide the quantitative dimension required for assessing the overall multi-risk value. EAR are categorized into four main groups:

- Population: Includes potential injuries and fatalities resulting from multi-hazard events.
- Environment: Covers the impact on natural resources, such as soil and water pollution, due to hazardous interactions.
- Infrastructure: Encompasses buildings, transportation networks, and equipment that may suffer structural or functional damage.

- **Economy:** Includes economic assets such as industries, businesses, and agricultural lands that could face financial losses.

This step emphasizes the identification and quantification of elements at risk (EAR) within the study area to provide a clear understanding of potential impacts in multi-hazard scenarios. Using a combination of statistical data, demographic profiles, and land use information, this process involves analyzing the location, characteristics, and exposure of vulnerable elements. The EAR include both physical assets, such as buildings and infrastructure, and socio-economic elements, such as population groups and essential services. To quantify the potential losses, monetary values are assigned to each EAR, using local or regional standards as a basis. This approach ensures flexibility and adaptability to the specific context of each study area. The outputs of this step include a detailed inventory of the identified EAR, their spatial distribution, and their associated quantified values. This comprehensive evaluation serves as a cornerstone for calculating multi-risk scenarios, enabling decision-makers to prioritize mitigation strategies effectively.

Step 7: Multi-risk value (MRV)

The multi-risk value (MRV) represents the final output of the multi-hazard risk assessment methodology, providing a comprehensive measure of the risk associated with each multi-hazard scenario. The MRV integrates three critical components: the Multi-Hazard Index (MHI), the Vulnerability Index (VI), and the quantified elements at risk (EAR). This combination captures the intensity of hazard interactions, the vulnerability of the affected area, and the economic value of exposed elements, resulting in an outcome expressed in monetary terms. Therefore, the MRV for each multi-hazard scenario is calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{MRV} = \text{MHI} \times \text{VI} \times \text{EAR (monetary value)} \quad (3)$$

Since the MHI and VI are indices, the MRV translates the combined hazard and vulnerability conditions into financial implications, aiding in the prioritization and management of risks.

The final output of this step is a diagram summarizing the MRVs for all multi-hazard scenarios, enabling the comparison and ranking of scenarios based on their financial and socio-economic impacts. The MRV provides a practical, actionable metric for decision-makers to allocate resources effectively and enhance resilience in post-mining areas by quantifying risk in monetary terms. For each identified scenario, the MRV is calculated by applying the above formula. The results can be represented visually using 2D or 3D diagrams to facilitate interpretation and decision making:

Two-dimensional Diagram

The vertical axis represents the product of the MHI and VI (see Figure 7).

The horizontal axis represents the monetary value of the EAR (see Figure 7).

This format provides a straightforward comparison of the overall risk level for each scenario.

Three-dimensional Diagram

The left and right vertical axes represent the MHI and VI, respectively (see Figure 8).

The horizontal axis depicts the monetary value of the EAR (see Figure 8).

This representation allows for a more detailed visualization of the interactions between the three components.

Figure 7. Illustration of MRV for each multi-hazard scenario in 2D diagram.

Figure 8. Illustration of MRV for each multi-hazard scenario in 3D diagram.

The assessment of the calculated Multi-Risk Values (MRVs) involves evaluating whether the identified risk levels are acceptable or require mitigation measures. This evaluation is guided by socio-economic criteria, regional and national standards, and the specific context of the case study in which the methodology is applied. The analysis enables the classification of scenarios into zones of acceptability by integrating monetary quantifications of potential losses. Diagrams can be developed to illustrate these zones, distinguishing between scenarios deemed acceptable and those requiring intervention. Acceptable scenarios reflect risks that align with societal resilience and regional or national thresholds, whereas unacceptable scenarios indicate a need for action to reduce potential impacts. Mitigation priorities are then established by selecting the scenarios requiring intervention, ensuring targeted efforts to enhance resilience. This structured approach provides a clear framework for decision making and aligns mitigation strategies with socio-economic and policy considerations.

2.5. Data Limitation

Data availability and quality are critical factors influencing the reliability of the multi-hazard risk assessment. Incomplete or inconsistent datasets can introduce uncertainties that affect the validity of risk evaluations. To mitigate these challenges, a combination of data harmonization, alternative data sources, and hybrid methodologies can be employed. Data harmonization involves standardizing datasets from different sources to improve consistency, while alternative data sources, such as remote sensing, hazard or elements at risk maps, statistical data and historical records, can supplement traditional datasets where gaps exist.

A hybrid approach can further enhance data reliability by integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques. This approach integrates qualitative and quantitative methods and offers a practical solution to data constraints. When precise numerical data are unavailable, expert judgment, stakeholder consultations, and semi-structured surveys can provide valuable insights, ensuring a more comprehensive assessment. Sequential designs allow for refining research questions by first exploring qualitative insights (e.g., expert interviews) before validating them through quantitative assessments. Alternatively, concurrent designs use both methods simultaneously, enabling data triangulation—cross-verifying findings from different sources to improve accuracy and identify inconsistencies. The proposed framework can remain adaptable and applicable across diverse post-mining environments, even in data-scarce regions, by adopting these strategies.

3. Discussion

The proposed multi-hazard risk assessment methodology represents a significant advancement in multi-risk management for post-mining areas. Unlike conventional single-hazard risk assessment, which evaluate hazards independently, this framework systematically integrates multiple interacting hazards, vulnerabilities, and elements at risk. Risk assessment is generally supported by quantitative methods, where risk is calculated based on probability and consequences. However, the proposed framework employs a semi-quantitative approach, where hazard intensity replaces probability, and consequences are determined as the product of vulnerability and elements at risk. This adaptation is necessary because quantitative methods are often impractical for post-mining areas and different types of interacting hazards, often due to a lack of data.

The selection of a semi-quantitative framework introduces certain limitations, particularly regarding subjectivity in the assignment of hazard interactions and intensity adjustments. However, this subjectivity is balanced by structured methodologies, expert-based assessments, and weighting techniques, ensuring a systematic and reproducible application of the framework. Moreover, the field of multi-hazard assessment has gained significant attention only in the last two decades, with ongoing research into methodologies capable of supporting complex hazard interdependencies. While multi-hazard risk assessment remains an active area of research, this study contributes to the evolution of risk assessment methodologies by applying a structured, semi-quantitative multi-hazard approach tailored to post-mining environments. It is one of the former frameworks tailored to the specific challenges of these landscapes, addressing the gap from previous studies that either lacked systematic integration or failed to cover the full spectrum of hazards, vulnerabilities, and risks. A novelty of this approach lies in the implementation of multi-hazard scenarios, which allow for a dynamic assessment of hazard interactions. While such scenarios have been partially addressed in broader multi-hazard methodologies, their systematic evaluation remains underexplored, and their application to post-mining areas is innovative. These aspects of risk assessment in post-mining areas, including the comparison with single-hazard risk analysis, have already been discussed in detail in the introduction. The introduction highlights the predominance of single-hazard assessments in post-mining risk analysis and underscores the necessity of a multi-hazard approach to capture hazard interactions and cascading effects.

The systematic integration of hazards, vulnerabilities, and elements at risk is a core strength of the methodology. The method captures the compounded effects of interacting hazards by quantifying adjusted hazard intensities and incorporating them into a multi-hazard index (MHI). The inclusion of a vulnerability index (VI) further ensures a comprehensive evaluation by considering both social and physical vulnerabilities, while the assessment of elements at risk translates the potential impacts into monetary terms. These

components collectively provide a robust framework for prioritizing risks and supporting decision making in complex hazard scenarios. Additionally, the method's adaptability is a notable strength. The flexibility for end-users to define weights for vulnerability indicators, input hazard interaction levels, and quantify elements at risk ensures that the framework can be tailored to diverse regional contexts. This adaptability enhances its practical application across various post-mining areas, providing a tool that is both scientifically rigorous and operationally feasible.

The proposed framework is designed to align with the European Green Deal by facilitating the sustainable transition of post-mining regions. The European Union has prioritized the reclamation of former coal mining areas through renewable energy projects, reforestation, and sustainable land management strategies. This framework provides a structured approach to managing multi-hazard risks associated with these transformations, ensuring safety and resilience in repurposed post-mining areas. Several real-world examples illustrate how risk assessment is essential in aligning redevelopment efforts with the Green Deal.

One example is the transformation of the Welzow-Süd lignite mine in Germany, where former coal extraction areas have been repurposed for renewable energy production, including large-scale solar and wind farms. The transition required thorough risk evaluations to address land subsidence, groundwater contamination, and soil degradation—challenges that the current framework systematically assesses. Similar efforts are underway in Poland's Silesia region, where former mining sites are being converted into research and innovation hubs, fostering green jobs while mitigating post-mining hazards.

This methodology ensures that such transformations account for cascading hazard effects, safeguarding long-term resilience. These examples illustrate how structured multi-hazard risk assessments, as presented in this study, are critical to achieving the European Green Deal's vision of sustainable, carbon-neutral land use transitions.

However, the methodology also faces certain limitations and challenges. One critical issue is the comparability of multi-hazard indices across scenarios with varying numbers of hazards. Scenarios involving more hazards tend to yield higher MHI values, which may not necessarily reflect a greater level of catastrophic potential. To address this, normalization could be employed, establishing upper and lower bounds for MHI values within groups of scenarios containing the same number of hazards.

Data availability and quality also remain significant challenges. The reliability of the methodology is contingent upon accurate and up-to-date input data, including hazard intensities, vulnerability indicators, and elements at risk. Inconsistencies or gaps in these datasets could skew results, particularly in regions with limited resources or irregular data collection practices. Furthermore, the reliance on linear interaction models for hazard intensities may not fully capture the complexity of cascading or compounding hazards, necessitating further refinement in future iterations. Despite these limitations, the framework does not seek to replace existing risk assessment methodologies but rather to enhance them. This approach contributes to the ongoing development of more comprehensive and adaptable risk management strategies, by integrating multi-hazard interactions and refining risk evaluation for post-mining areas. Finally, while the flexibility afforded to end-users is an asset, it also introduces a degree of subjectivity. Decisions regarding weights, interaction levels, and risk quantification may vary based on the expertise and priorities of individual users, potentially affecting the consistency of results.

4. Conclusions

The methodology presented in this work offers a robust and systematic framework for assessing multi-hazard risks in post-mining areas, addressing the complex interactions

among hazards and their impacts on socio-economic and environmental stability. The methodology bridges the gap between theoretical frameworks and practical applications, enabling stakeholders to manage and mitigate risks effectively by integrating a semi-quantitative approach with flexible tools.

One of the significant contributions of this work is its emphasis on a semi-quantitative approach, enabling the application of the methodology in areas with limited data availability. A key achievement is the development of a structured seven-step process that guides users from hazard identification and susceptibility analysis to the final assessment of multi-risk values. This process incorporates innovative techniques such as interaction matrices, adjusted intensity principles, and indicator-based vulnerability assessments, ensuring that the methodology is both adaptable and comprehensive. The integration of social and physical vulnerability indices, alongside elements at risk quantified in monetary terms, ensures that socio-economic and environmental dimensions are adequately addressed. This approach not only enhances the robustness of risk assessments but also supports decision-makers in prioritizing mitigation measures and allocating resources effectively.

The development of Multi-Hazard Index (MHI) and Multi-Risk Value (MRV) calculations offers practical insights into the severity and socio-economic implications of hazard scenarios. These indices serve as foundational metrics for understanding and comparing multi-risk levels, guiding targeted interventions to enhance the safety and resilience of post-mining areas. Furthermore, the methodology aligns with the objectives of the European Green Deal, promoting sustainable land management and supporting coal-dependent regions in their transition toward a carbon-neutral economy.

Despite its strengths, the methodology acknowledges limitations, including data quality constraints, challenges in standardizing hazard interaction levels, and the non-comparability of Multi-Hazard Indices (MHIs) across scenarios with differing hazard counts. Proposed solutions, such as normalization techniques, enhance the methodology's robustness and applicability, ensuring meaningful comparisons of multi-risk levels. Looking ahead, the implementation of the methodology in future research of post-mining case studies will further validate its effectiveness and adaptability. The implementation of tools such as GIS and decision-making methods will enhance its capacity to address the unique challenges of post-mining areas, supporting stakeholders in achieving long-term socio-economic and environmental stability.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, D.M.N.-S. and A.I.T.; methodology, D.M.N.-S.; validation, D.M.N.-S., A.I.T. and I.E.Z.; writing—original draft preparation, D.M.N.-S.; writing—review and editing, A.I.T., I.E.Z. and N.C.K.; supervision, I.E.Z. and N.C.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel under the project POMHAZ No 101057326. Financial assistance from the European Commission is much appreciated. The first author also received funding under a PhD Scholarship provided by the Research Committee of NTUA (ELKE-NTUA).

Data Availability Statement: Data is contained within the article.

Acknowledgments: The authors are grateful to Marwan Al Heib for fruitful discussions on multi-hazard analysis in post-mining areas.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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